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Molecular Detection of Virulence and Antibiotic Resistance Genes in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Isolated from Clinical Samples: A Cross-Sectional Study Conducted at General Hospital Aliero, Kebbi State, North-west Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Klebsiella pneumoniae is a significant pathogen that causes severe, difficult-to-treat diseases. The emergence and spread of virulence and antibiotic resistance genes has resulted public health concern epidemics and transmission of antibiotic-resistant organisms. A total of 259 clinical specimens from patients were examined. The quantitative phenotypic method was used to assess hemolysin production and hyper mucus-viscosity (HV), disk diffusion method and double disc synergy test were used for antibiotic susceptibility testing and Extended Spectrum Beta-lactamase (ESBLs) producing *K. pneumoniae* isolates. Out of 259 samples, 32 turn out to be *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, 15 (46.90%) of the 32 *K. pneumoniae* are evaluated positive for hemolysin production, and 3 (9.4%) tested positive for hyper mucus-viscosity. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* showed lowest resistance to imipenem (6.3%), meropenem (9.3%) and ciprofloxacin (28.1%), however, (56.2%) were resistant to cefotaxime, (53.1%) to cefpodoxime, and tetracycline. On the other hand, 19 (59.4%) of the 32 *K. pneumoniae* isolates tested positive for ESBLs. 14 (82.4%), 9 (52.9%), and 5 (29.4%) isolates were found to carry virulence factor genes, such as *fimH*, *RmpA*, and *BssS*. Subsequently, antimicrobial resistance genes encoding ESBLs producing enzymes like *blaSHV*, *blaTEM* and *blaCTX-M* were 18 (94.7%), 10 (52.6%) and 3 (15.8%) were detected among the isolates. This study ascertains the worrisome presence of antibiotic resistant strains and the present of virulence and resistance genes. As a result, emergency stewardship programs to monitor antimicrobial resistance patterns in General Hospital Aliero facility is required.

Keywords: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, virulence factor, Antibiotic resistance genes, and ESBLs

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Klebsiella pneumoniae belongs to bacterial domain and is a facultative anaerobic, encapsulated, lactose fermenting bacillus that is Gram-negative (Davoudabadi *et al.*, 2023). When it was first isolated in 1875 by a German physician and bacteriologist named "Theodor Albrech Edwin Klebs," it was later described by Carl Friedländer in 1882, which led to it being known for a while as Friedlander's bacillus. Later, in 1885, Trevisan V. named the genus *Klebsiella* in honor of Theodor Albrech Edwin Klebs (Muhammad *et al.*, 2024a). The bacteria *K. pneumoniae* are medically recognized as one of the most important opportunistic pathogens, causing hospital and community-acquired infections worldwide, including not limited to

pulmonary, urinary tract, blood, soft tissue, pyogenic liver abscesses, burn, and wound infections (Kiran *et al.*, 2022).

Furthermore, this species of bacteria uses a variety of defense mechanisms to fend off host immune responses as a result of having several virulent factors (Suyeon *et al.*, 2023). These include capsules, lipopolysaccharides (LPS), siderophores, and fimbriae. The capsule is widely acknowledged as a significant virulence factor that aids in the defense against environmental stressors, host immune responses, and antibiotic resistance. Although *K. pneumoniae*'s outer surface is coated in lipopolysaccharides, the sensation of LPS is what causes an inflammatory cascade to be released to the host organism and has been shown to be a major cause of sepsis and septic sequelae (Anand *et al.*, 2020). Through a specific virulence component called fimbriae, the pathogen can attach itself to host cells (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2020). Siderophores use the iron they get from their host to help the contaminated organism spread (Liu *et al.*, 2020). According to Davoudabadi *et al.* (2023), the development of virulence factors and the increase in antibiotic resistance make treating *K. pneumoniae* infections more difficult. The presence of virulence genes in *K. pneumoniae* is linked to its pathogenicity; these genes encode particular virulence factors that enable the bacterium to attack the immune system and cause a range of diseases (Wang *et al.*, 2020).

K. pneumoniae is given a hypermucoviscous phenotype by the plasmid gene *RmpA* (regulator of mucoid phenotype A), which increases the production of capsular polysaccharides. Colonies that create length of greater than 5 millimeter mucous strings when touched with a bacteriological loop are easily identified as hypermucoviscous strains of *K. pneumoniae* using the string test (Derakhshan *et al.*, 2016). Certain virulence-associated genes, such as the type 3 and type 1 adhesins gene (*fimH*) and the biofilm formation gene (*BssS*), are crucial for the production of capsular polysaccharides, invasion, adhesion, and biofilm formation of *K. pneumoniae* isolates. These genes are also crucial for the pathogenicity of *K. pneumoniae* isolates from infections obtained in both community and hospital settings (Paczosa *et al.*, 2016). Likewise, *K. pneumoniae* strains are becoming more resistant to antibiotics (Davoudabadi *et al.*, 2023). According to the World Health Organization's worldwide monitoring report on antibiotic resistance, *K. pneumoniae*, primarily in hospital settings, exhibited over (50%) resistance to third-generation cephalosporins in five of the six WHO regions. Additionally, the study found that *K. pneumoniae* resistant to third-generation cephalosporins was linked to higher mortality rates in South East Asia (81%) and the Western Pacific region (72%), the Eastern Mediterranean region (50%), and Africa (77%). Additionally, it stated that multi-drug resistant (MDR) bacteria were responsible for (45%) of mortality in South-East Asia and Africa. According to WHO (2017) and Founou *et al.* (2017), these resistant strains constitute a public health concern that need attention. In order to fight off commonly used antibiotics, Gram-negative bacteria, such as *K. pneumoniae*, have also developed a number of antibiotic resistance mechanisms, such as the acquisition of genes that confer resistance to antibiotics, such as extended-spectrum beta lactamase (ESBLs). Epidemiological studies showed that *K. pneumoniae* strains, especially those isolated from disease classified as hospital-acquired, have a high rate of resistance to the commonly used antibiotic group penicillins (Davoudabadi *et al.*, 2023). Since the extended-spectrum beta lactamase genes (*blaSHV*, *blaTEM*, and *blaCTX-M*) of *K. pneumoniae* are plasmid-encoded and have demonstrated resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, including penicillin, they are believed to be multidrug resistant. According to Alhassan *et al.* (2024), *K. pneumoniae* has a considerable capacity to acquire and spread antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes, mostly by horizontal gene transfer. Antibiotic resistant pathogens, along with their genes for virulence and resistance, have therefore arisen and are still gaining more attention worldwide (Okafor *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, it is important to ascertain their gene profile, especially that of *K. pneumoniae* (Hosu *et al.*, 2021). However, there is limited information on the virulence and resistance genes profile of *K. pneumoniae* isolated from Nigeria. As a result of that, this study was focus on assessing the antibiotic susceptibility patterns, as well as resistance and virulence genes profile in *K. pneumoniae* isolated from clinical specimen of patient attending General Hospital Aiero, Kebbi State, Nigeria.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Clinical Specimens and Primary Identification

Two hundred and fifty-nine 259 clinical specimens were obtained from patients of (120 males and 139 females, of ages range from 5 to 90 years), of which 32 *K. pneumoniae* bacteria were isolated, 10 from urine specimens, 13 from respiratory samples, 7 from wound specimens, and 2 from blood specimens. The specimens were obtained aseptically from General Hospital Aliero in Nigeria, Kebbi State. And the study area was located between the axis, latitude of 12° 16' 42" North and a longitude of 4° 27' 6" 1 East relative to the equator, its total land area spans about 412 square kilometers, accommodating an estimated population of approximately 125,783 individuals (NPC, 2006). Prior to specimens' collection, ethical approval was obtained from Kebbi State Health Research Ethics Committee (KSHREC) with the reference number MOH/KSREC/VOLI/56 and KSHREC registration number 107:017/2023. Additionally, the samples were collected between April 2023 to October 2024. The bacteria was isolated from sputum, wounds, urine, and blood specimens upon cultured on MacConkey, Blood, and Cystine-Lactose-Electrolyte-Deficient Agar (CLED) Agar (Oxoid UK), using lactose-fermenting mucoid colonies on MacConkey's and CLED agars, then Gram-negative rods examined under a microscope following staining, and a series of biochemical reactions such as (Methyl Red, Voges-Proskauer, Simmons Citrate, Chritensen's urease, and motility tests), as a basis of classical Microbiological identification of *K. pneumoniae* and in accordance with the protocol adopted from (Cheesbrough, 2010; Tille *et al.*, 2017). Then Molecular analysis using conventional Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR).

Phenotypic Detection of Virulence Factors

Detection of Hemolysin Production

The *K. pneumoniae* isolates was evaluated on blood agar in order to determine which isolates produced hemolysin. The bacteria were culture on 5% sheep blood agar and then incubated at 37°C for 18 to 24 hours. The synthesis of hemolysin that is (β -hemolysis) was determined by the existence of complete clear zone of erythrocytes surrounding the colonies (Zaghloul *et al.*, 2021).

Hyper Mucoviscosity (HMV) Modified String Test

The hyper mucoviscous (HMV) trait was established using the string test. Briefly an overnight, isolates were cultured on MacConkey agar at 37°C for 18 to 24 hours. A mucoviscous string was then stretched vertically from a colony using an inoculation loop; the development of a viscous string measuring more than 5 mm was indicative of HMV positive phenotype (Balle'n *et al.*, 2021).

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

The disc diffusion method was used to test for antibiotic susceptibility on Mueller-Hinton agar (Oxoid UK) using antibiotic discs in accordance with the Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute's (CLSI, 2024) criteria. Cefpodoxime (CPD 10 μ g), Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid (20/10 μ g), Cefotaxime (CTX, 5 μ g), Ceftriaxone (CXM, 30 μ g), Ceftazidime (30 μ g + 6 μ g), Cefuroxime (CXM, 30 μ g), Tetracycline (TTR 30 μ g), Imipenem (IMP, 10 μ g), Meropenem (MEM, 10 μ g), Ciprofloxacin (CIP, 5 μ g), and Amikacin (AMK, 30 μ g) were used to test the isolates. Prior to applying the antibiotic discs, the test isolates were made as a suspension and were adjusted to 0.5 MacFarland turbidity standards, and aseptically inoculated onto Muller-Hinton agar plates using sterile swab sticks. Within 15 minutes of inoculation of the plates, then the Plates was incubated at 37°C for 18 to 24 hrs. Following incubation, the clear zone diameter surrounding the disc was measured using transmitted light, and the results were interpreted in line with (CLSI, 2024).

Phenotypic Detection of Extended Spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs) in *K. pneumoniae* isolates

The double disc synergy test (DDST) was used in this study to identify ESBLs producing *K. pneumoniae*. In short, the test isolates were prepared as suspension upon adjusting into 0.5 turbidity standards, then aseptically were also inoculated in Muller-Hinton agar (Oxoid UK), plates using sterile swab sticks, then after amoxicillin/clavulanic acid discs (20 μ g /10 μ g) and third-generation cephalosporin discs (ceftazidime 30 μ g, cefotaxime 5 μ g and Cefuroxime 30 μ g) was placed on the prepared agar plate at the distance of about 15 mm apart, and each plate was incubated overnight at 37° C for 18 to 24 hours. The presence of an

increase in the cephalosporin inhibition zone toward the amoxicillin/clavulanic acid disc was considered a positive indicator for ESBLs enzymes producing *K. pneumoniae* (Eman Marzouk *et al.*, 2024).

Genomic DNA extraction

With some adjustments, the Muhammad *et al.* (2024a) thermal lysis method was used to extract the DNA. Two to five (2-5) fresh colonies of the test bacteria were suspended to 150 Microliter (μL) of molecular grade water in PCR tube. After that, a thermal cycler was used to heat the PCR tube after covering the cover of the Eppendorf tube with paraffin wax for 20 minutes at 98°C . Following a five minute centrifugation at 14,000 Revolution per minutes (rpm) to pelletize the cell debris, the supernatant was placed into sterile, labeled Eppendorf tubes and kept at -20°C for additional processing (Muhammad *et al.*, 2024b).

Determination of DNA Concentration

A spectrophotometer was used to measure the quantity of light that DNA absorbed at about 260 nanometer (nm) (A260) in order to calculate the concentration of DNA. When the ratio of A260/A280 for dsDNA was between approximately 1.8 and 2.0 wavelengths, it was deemed pure; while a ratio below 1.7 would suggest protein or RNA contamination (Farkhanda1 *et al.*, 2019; Muhammad *et al.* 2024a).

Molecular Detection of *K. pneumoniae* Virulence and Resistance Genes

Pure genomic DNA of *K. pneumoniae* extracted was used as the template for the PCR, which was carried out using primer in Table 1 and Master Mix ready to load (Solis Biodyne, Estonia) to amplify the *BssS*, *RmpA*, *fimH*, *blaSHV*, *blaTEM* and *blaCTX-M*, genes in *K. pneumoniae* isolates. A total amount of $25\ \mu\text{L}$ was used for the PCR, which included $12.5\ \mu\text{L}$ of the Solis Biodyne Master Mix (Solis Biodyne, Estonia) that was ready to load, $1\ \mu\text{L}$ of forward and reverse primers, $5\ \mu\text{L}$ of template DNA, and $5.5\ \mu\text{L}$ of molecular grade water, for a total of $25\ \mu\text{L}$ of PCR solution. Initial denaturation at 95°C for 15 minutes, 30 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 54°C for 30 seconds, extension at 72°C for 4 minutes, and final extension at 72°C for 10 minutes comprised the temperature and time conditions of the DNA amplification. To separate the amplification product, ten microliters ($10\ \mu\text{L}$) of the PCR products and $10\ \mu\text{L}$ of DNA ladder ready to load (Solis Biodyne, Estonia) were used, followed by electrophoresis on 1.5% and $0.5\times$ TBE buffer, agarose gel with $10\ \mu\text{L}$ of SYBR dye pipetted into a well created with comb. Electrophoresis was performed at 90 volts for 30 minutes, and the DNA amplicon was examined with UV trans-illuminator, with modifications based on the methodology of (Okafor *et al.*, 2023).

Table 1. Primer used for amplification of Virulence and ESBLs genes.

Gene	Primer sequence (5' → 3')	Amplicons size (bp)	Refences
<i>BssS</i>	Forward: AGCTACGATGCGCTGATGTT Reverse: CAATCTTCGCAATGCCTGCT	148	Dalir <i>et al.</i> 2021
<i>RmpA</i>	Forward: ACTGGGCTACCTCTGCTTCA Reverse: CTTGCATGAGCCATCTTTCA	516	Derakhshan <i>et al.</i> 2016
<i>fimH</i>	Forward: ATCGTTAATCGCGGTGCTGA Reverse: GGAGGCGGTATTGGTGAAGA	274	Dalir <i>et al.</i> 2021
<i>blaCTX-M</i>	Forward: CGCTTTGCGATGTGCAG Reverse: ACCGCGATATCGTTGGT	551	Turugurwa <i>et al.</i> 2019
<i>blaSHV</i>	Forward: ATGCGTTATATTCGCCTGTG Reverse: TGCTTTGTTATTCGGGCCAA	972	Turugurwa <i>et al.</i> 2019
<i>blaTEM</i>	Forward: TCGCCGCATACACTATTCTCAGAATGA Reverse: ACGCTCACCGGCTCCAGATTTAT	560	Muhammad <i>et al.</i> 2024a

Statistical Analysis

Microsoft Office Excel 2010 software was used to record the data and calculate the frequencies. The qualitative variables were represented in frequency table and chart were necessary.

3.0 RESULTS

Prevalence of *K. pneumoniae* Isolated

K. pneumoniae isolates were obtained from 32 of the 259 clinical specimens; 18 of these isolates were obtained from female patients (56.25%) and 15 from male patients (43.75%). The patients' ages ranges from 5 to 26 years, 5 (15.6%) were recorded, then followed by age range of 27 to 47 years with 7 (21.9%), 48 to 68 years, 14 (43.7%), and 69 to 90 years, with 6 (18.8%) years, respectively. However, 10 (31.2%) were isolated from urine samples, while 13 (40.60%) from respiratory samples, were 7 (21.9%) from wound samples, and 2 (6.2%) blood samples were the source of isolates.

Table 2. Prevalence of *K. pneumoniae* based on specimen type

Specimens	Number of <i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Percentages (%)
Urine	10	31.25
Respiratory	13	40.62
Wound	7	21.88
Blood	2	6.25

Table 3. Prevalence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* based on age

Age group	Number of <i>K. pneumoniae</i>	Percentages (%)
2-25	5	15.62
27-47	7	21.87
48-68	14	43.75
69-90	6	18.75

Prevalence of Phenotypic Detection of Virulence Factors in *K. pneumoniae* Isolates

Detection of Hemolysin Production: Out of the 32 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates from the total 259 clinical specimens, only 15 (46.90%) tested positive in the hemolysin test, while 17 (53.1%) tested negative as shows in Table 4.

Hypermucoviscosity (HV) test: Of the 32 clinical isolates tested for hyper mucu-viscosity, 3 (9.4%) tested positive and 29 (90.6%) tested negative as indicated in Table 4 as showed below respectively.

Table 4. Prevalence of Phenotypic Virulence Factors in *K. pneumoniae* Isolated (n=32)

Virulence Test	Negative Isolates (%)	Positive Isolates (%)
Hemolytic	17 (53.1%)	15 (46.90%)
Hypermucoviscosity	29 (90.6%)	3 (9.4%)

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test: Muller-Hinton agar plates were used to assess the antibiotic sensitivity pattern of thirty-two (32) confirmed *K. pneumoniae* isolates from clinical specimens. As illustrated in Figure 1, strains were divided into three groups based on their antibiotic resistance pattern: as susceptible (S), resistant (R), and intermediate (I). Eleven (11) different antibiotics was used, and the results of the 32 isolates are summarized below. However, the resistance pattern test showed that the highest levels of resistance were against Cefotaxime (56.2%), then followed by Cefpodoxime (53.1%), and Tetracycline (53.1%), while the lowest levels were recorded against Imipenem (6.3%), Meropenem (9.3%), and Ciprofloxacin (28.1%), as the sensitive drugs as showed below respectively.

Figure 1.

Prevalence of Extended Spectrum Beta-lactamase’s (ESBLs) Producing *K. pneumoniae*:

The ESBLs phenotypes test was carried out during the course of the study were found to be positive in 19 (59.4%) isolates which demonstrating a high prevalence of ESBLs production in *K. pneumoniae* isolated, in the study area respectively.

PCR Results of Virulence Genes:

The results of the assessment of virulence factors genes showed that, of the 17 positive isolates found during the phenotypic test of hemolysin and hypermucoviscous test, the most common gene among all clinical isolates identified were *fimH*, with 14 (82.4%), then followed by *RmpA*, with 9 (52.9%), and *BssS*, with 5 (29.4%).

PCR Results of Antimicrobial Resistance Genes:

The PCR analysis of all isolates that were phenotypically positive for EBLs production test, out of the 19 *K. pneumoniae* strain, illustrate that 18 (94.7%) carried ESBLs-encoding gene of *blaSHV* while 10 (52.6%) isolates have *blaTEM* encoding gene and subsequently 3 (15.8%), been the least isolates that carried the *blaCTX-M* ESBLs-encoding gene respectively.

Figure 2. PCR Results of Virulence and Resistance Genes

4.0 DISCUSSION

Within the Enterobacteriaceae family, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is a significant species that causes infections in hospitals and community settings both in immunocompetent and immunocompromised patients. During the study we found that it causes infections both in young and old adults upon our current investigation. In this study, 32 *K. pneumoniae* isolates which is (12.4%) were identified from the four clinical specimens. In terms of isolation rate, our study is comparable to that of Nakaye *et al.* (2014), who reported a prevalence rate of (12.7%), and with that of Dalir *et al.* (2021), who also reported a prevalence rate of (15.5%) of *K. pneumoniae* isolates. The bacterium isolated in this investigation is widely distributed in nature, has been linked to nosocomial infections, and is easily acquired and spread by unsanitary circumstances in the community and hospital settings (Orole *et al.*, 2020). Any etiologic agent's prevalence can differ between different geographic locations or even within the same geographic location (Akingbade *et al.*, 2012). Our current study does, however, differ from earlier research study conducted at Sir Yahaya Memorial Hospital Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, where the frequency of occurrence of *K. pneumonia* was about (10.0%) (Danlami *et al.*, 2019), and from earlier research at Tertiary Care Hospital in Bangladesh, where *K. pneumonia* isolates, obtained from blood, urine, wound swabs, sputum, and endotracheal aspirates, with a prevalence rate of 75 (23.73) (Sonia *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, 66 that is (33%) were reported at Dalhatu Araf Specialist Hospital (DASH), Lafia, Nasarawa State (Orole *et al.*, 2020); and 12 (41.4%) were reported at Dutse General Hospital, Jigawa State, Nigeria (Muhammad *et al.*, 2019); and with research conducted at Edo State, Southern, Nigeria, which also reported prevalence of 31 (44.28%) (Osagie *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, another study that was carried out at the Tertiary Care Hospital in Jaipur, Rajasthan, India, found that the prevalence was about 30.15 percent (Ashina *et al.*, 2021). These variations in isolation rates can therefore be attributed to either changes in geographic area or variations in sample size. The virulence factors of *K. pneumoniae* isolates were identified using classical phenotypic techniques. Ability to prevent phagocytosis, bacteria virulence factors contribute significantly to the pathophysiology especially in the case of *K. pneumoniae* bacteria it uses virulence factors to facilitate the effective establishment of infection (Sá-Pessoa *et al.*, 2025). Additionally, because it takes into account one of the resistance mechanisms, it is a crucial line for researchers today (Cepas *et al.*, 2020). The Prevalence of phenotypic determination of virulence factors in *K. pneumoniae* reveal that Hypermucoviscosity phenotype, phenomenon was observed slightly in 3 (9.4%), partially similar report was previously reported by Balle'n *et al.* (2021) who detect HV in (13.39%). The strains of hypermucoviscous phenotype are considered hypervirulent strains (Ma *et al.*, 2025). And comparatively slightly different result was also obtained by Victor *et al.* (2007) who reported mucoid phenotype in more than (90%) of isolates in human with acquired pneumonia in South Africa.

Furthermore, detection of hemolytic activity of *K. pneumoniae* isolates represented an important virulence factor, as production of hemolysin (Zaghloul *et al.*, 2020). In this study, the hemolytic activity of *K. pneumoniae* isolates were detected in 15 (46.90%) isolates. This report is in line with a study conducted at El-Behira governorate, Damanhur, Egypt (22.9 %) isolates was recoded from clinical source as reported by (Zaghloul *et al.*, 2020). Pathogenicity of *K. pneumoniae* has been attributed to the possession and production of resistance genes, virulence genes, integrons, production of toxins (Firoozeh *et al.*, 2019). The genes for Extended Spectrum Beta-Lactamases, specifically *blaSHV*, *blaCTX-M* and *blaTEM*, isolated from *Klebsiella pneumoniae* increases the bacteria's resistance and pathogenicity (Orole *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates found in this investigation showed varied levels of antibiotic resistance. Cefotaxime (56.2%), Cefpodoxime (53.1%), and Cefoxitin (53.1%) had the highest resistance among the isolated *K. pneumoniae* strains. Ceftazidime (50.0%), Amikacin (46.8%), and Ceftriaxone (43.70%) were next in line. This study's findings are somewhat similar regarding ceftazidime (83.9%) (Danlami *et al.*, 2019). Cefexime 23/49 (46.9%), Cefotaxime 26/49 (53.0%), Ciprofloxacin 32/49 (65.3%), and Ceftazidime 27/49 (55.1%) were also reported by Nasarawa State (Ngwai *et al.*, 2023). Likewise, to Ciprofloxacin 67 (89.33%), Cefotaxime 54 (72.00%), and Ceftazidime 56 (74.67%) were reported by Sonia *et al.* (2020), whereas Cefotaxime 26 (53.0%), Ciprofloxacin 32 (65.3%), Ceftazidime 27 (55.1), and Cefexime 23 (46.9%) were reported by Ngwai *et al.* (2023).

However, the study also found a high rate of susceptibility to some of the antibiotic agents tested. The susceptibility profile shows that the most effective antibacterial agents were imipenem (93.6%) and meropenem (90.7%), followed by ciprofloxacin (71.9%). This finding is consistent with a prior study from Lafia, Nasarawa State, which found that imipenem was the most sensitive drug, scoring 41/49 (83.67%), whereas Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid scored 18/49 (36.73%) (Ngwai *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, a prior study in a Bangladeshi tertiary care hospital found that Imipenem and Meropenem had 47/75 (62.66%) each, followed by Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid with 19/75 (25.33%), which is different from what we found (Sonia *et al.*, 2020). Although the incidence of ESBLs among clinical isolates varies widely globally and geographically and is changing quickly over time, as the prevalence of phenotypic ESBLs-Producing *K. pneumoniae* was established (Turugurwa *et al.*, 2019). The present study is in consistent with a study by Zaghloul *et al.* (2021) were reported (56.3%) of ESBLs-producing *K. pneumoniae* in the facility, as well as with another study in Zaria that reported (40.7%) of ESBLs-producing *K. pneumoniae* (Giwa *et al.*, 2018) and (40.7%) in Port Harcourt Southern, Nigeria (Onanuga *et al.*, 2019). The percentage of ESBLs production in various *K. pneumoniae* isolates was positive, with 19 (59.4%) isolates which demonstrating a high prevalence of ESBLs production in *K. pneumoniae* in the facility during the study. And a prior study in Pakistan found that the percentage of *K. pneumoniae* that produced ESBLs was higher than our present study with (71.7%). Additionally, Ilorin reported that roughly (26.5%) of *K. pneumoniae* produced ESBLs, which is significantly different from our findings (Fadeyi *et al.*, 2016). These discrepancies may be the result of geographical and behavioral attitudes on the prescription and use of antibiotics, particularly cephalosporins, in both community and hospital settings. The study's findings on the molecular detection of virulence genes in *K. pneumoniae* isolates particularly *FimH* (fimbriae gene), *RmpA* (hypermucoviscosity), and *BssS* (biofilm formation) showed that genes involved in biofilm formation and contributing to the rise in antibiotic resistance *FimH* were 14 (82.4%), which was found to be the most frequently detected virulence factor gene, then followed by *RmpA* gene with 9 (52.9%) and *BssS* gene 5 (29.4%) of the *K. pneumoniae* isolates. This data is comparable to a study conducted by Dalir *et al.* (2021) were the prevalence rate for the *fimH* gene was (93.33%) and that of *BssS* gene was present in 56 hospitalized patients in Babol, Iran, with frequencies of *FimH* (86.1%) and *RmpA* (10.8%). Consequently, our study differs slightly from the findings of Davoudabadi *et al.* (2023) about the *fimH* gene with (86.5%), as well as from another study by Liaqat *et al.* (2021) regarding *fimH* (80.0%), Ballen *et al.* (2021) which reported (98.4%), as well as Remya *et al.* (2019) (89.1%), and Zhang *et al.* (85.5%) respectively. However, Resistance genes, virulence genes, integrons, and toxin production have all been implicated in the pathogenicity of resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* as well as extended spectrum beta-lactamases genes from isolated resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* including *blaTEM*, *blaSHV*, and *blaCTX-M* (Firoozeh *et al.*, 2019). And hence these genes promote virulence and resistance in the bacteria hence (Orole *et al.*, 2020).

Additionally, the polymerase chain reaction analysis revealed that the majority of the phenotypically positive ESBLs isolates had genes for the Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamases such as *blaSHV*, *blaTEM*, and *blaCTX-M* among others. As a result of that during our present study *blaSHV* gene was the most prevalent were present in 18 which is (94.7%), followed by *blaTEM* with 10 (52.6%) and *blaCTX-M* (Active on Cefotaxime), which was the least prevalent gene, found in 3 (15.8%) isolates. Regarding *blaSHV* with 37 (71.2%) and *blaTEM* 44 (84.6%), this result is comparable to the findings of Davoudabadi *et al.* (2023); however, they differ in with *blaCTX-M* 28 (53.8%), additionally, it differs in comparison to *TEM* (48.5%), *blaSHV* (57.6%), and *blaCTX-M* (72.7%) (Orole *et al.*, 2020). However, Okafor *et al.* (2023) recorded (16.90%) in *blaTEM* (12.67%) *blaSHV* and *blaCTX-M* with (9.15%) is comparatively differs from our present study. These genes are essential for giving bacteria resistance against several antibiotic drugs, such as Imipenem, Meropenem, third-generation cephalosporins, and other medicines Alhassan *et al.* (2024).

5. CONCLUSION

One of the most significant pathogens, *K. pneumoniae*, produces a wide range of illnesses, both hospital and community, and is frequently linked to nosocomial outbreaks. It also exhibits varying levels of virulence and drug resistance. Furthermore, the public health community has a significant issue with the rise of infections caused by *K. pneumoniae* that are difficult to cure. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to evaluate the identification of certain virulence factor genes and antibiotic resistance genes that specifically encode extended spectrum beta-lactamase-producing enzymes in the *K. pneumoniae* bacteria that were isolated from various clinical specimens of patients who were admitted to General Hospital Aliero Kebbi State. It is difficult to treat infections brought on by isolated, isolates of *K. pneumoniae* that possess these virulence and resistance genes The current study highlights the importance of finding effective solutions to combat antibiotic resistance, given the high prevalence of virulence and antibiotic resistance genes, particularly β -lactamase-encoding genes, among isolates with high virulence factors. Above all, new and reliable diagnostic approaches for detecting the virulence and antibiotic resistance genes of *K. pneumoniae* bacteria should be developed.

Disclosure of Conflict of Interest:

All authors declare no competing interests

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